

Approximate regularised maximum-likelihood approach for censoring outliers

eISSN 2051-3305
 Received on 25th February 2019
 Revised 12th June 2019
 Accepted on 13th June 2019
 E-First on 24th September 2019
 doi: 10.1049/joe.2019.0717
 www.ietdl.org

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Abstract: This study considers censoring outliers in a radar scenario with limited sample support. The problem is formulated as obtaining the regularised maximum likelihood (RML) estimate of the outlier index set. Since the RML estimate involves solving a combinatorial optimisation problem, a reduced complexity but approximate RML (ARML) procedure is also devised. As to the selection of the regularisation parameter, the cross-validation technique is exploited. At the analysis stage, the performance of the RML/ARML procedure is evaluated based both on simulated and challenging knowledge-aided sensor signal processing and expert reasoning data, also in comparison with some other outlier excision methods available in the open literature. The numerical results highlight that the RML/ARML algorithm achieves a satisfactory performance level in the presence of limited as well as sufficient sample supports whereas the other counterparts often experience a certain performance degradation for the insufficient training volume.

1 Introduction

A set of secondary data is often required to estimate the unknown interference parameters of the primary data in many adaptive radar processing techniques such as constant false alarm rate detectors [1–3], direction-of-arrival estimation [4] and space-time adaptive processing [5]. The training data are typically selected from range cells spatially adjacent to the cell under test (CUT) and assumed to be homogeneous, namely, statistically independent and identically distributed. Unfortunately, the homogeneous assumption is often violated in practical applications due to the presence of non-homogeneity such as varying terrain, clutter discretises, moving targets and so on. These deleterious components are normally referred to as outliers since they may produce returns whose statistical characteristics are radically different from those of the homogeneous data. In the presence of outliers, the training data are no longer representative of the interference in the CUT, which will cause some performance degradation of the training data-based algorithms [6]. As a result, censoring outliers is a crucial task for overcoming the adverse effects of a non-homogeneous environment. However, the existing outlier censorship techniques, such as the generalised inner product (GIP) [7], the reiterative censored GIP (RCGIP) [8], the approximate maximum likelihood (AML) [9] and the exact maximum likelihood (ML) [9], generally require that the number of training data is sufficiently high (at least twice the system degrees of freedom (DOFs) [10]) in order to ensure a satisfactory performance level, which may restrict their practical applications when the system DOFs are large.

In this study, we focus on the problem of outlier excision and consider a non-homogeneous radar scenario with limited training data. Specifically, we derive the regularised maximum likelihood (RML) estimate of the outlier index set resorting to the generalised regularised likelihood function (GRLF) criterion. The regularised penalty is exploited in order to ensure well-conditioned estimates in the case of insufficient sample support. The RML estimate requires solving a combinatorial optimisation problem whose computational burden is heavy. In order to circumvent this problem, we design a reduced complexity but approximate RML (ARML) procedure. As to the selection of the regularisation parameter, we exploit the cross-validation (CV) technique [11, 12],

which relies on partitioning the secondary data into two subsets. The former is used as training to derive the RML outlier index estimate and the corresponding RML interference covariance estimate whereas the latter plays the role of validation set to evaluate the risk associated with the obtained covariance estimate. At the analysis stage, we assess the performance of the RML and ARML procedures in the presence of simulated as well as challenging knowledge-aided sensor signal processing and expert reasoning (KASSPER) data [13], also in comparison with GIP, RCGIP, AML and ML algorithms.

Notation: In the paper, vectors and matrices are denoted by bold-italic face lower-case and upper-case letters, respectively.

Symbols $\det(\cdot)$, $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$, $(\cdot)^H$, and $(\cdot)^{-1}$ denote the determinant, trace, conjugate transpose, and inverse, respectively. Given matrix \mathbf{R} of size $N \times N$, $\lambda_i(\mathbf{R})$, $i = 1, \dots, N$, denotes the eigenvalues of \mathbf{R} . Finally, for a finite set A , $|A|$ stands for its cardinality.

2 Design of the regularised outlier censoring scheme

Consider a radar system equipped with N channels (spatial and/or temporal) which collects data from K distinct range cells. The N -dimensional sample from the i th ($i = 1, \dots, K$) range cell is denoted as \mathbf{x}_i and modelled as

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{c}_i, & \forall i \in \Omega - \Omega_0 \\ \mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{c}_i + \mathbf{p}_i, & \forall i \in \Omega_0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{c}_1, \dots, \mathbf{c}_K$ are independent complex Gaussian random vectors with mean 0 and covariance matrix \mathbf{R} (assumed to be positive definite and modelled as an unknown deterministic parameter), representing the homogeneous interference components; $\Omega = \{1, \dots, K\}$ is a K -dimensional set including the indices of all the considered range cells; $\Omega_0 = \{i_1, \dots, i_M\}$ is a M ($M \leq K$)-dimensional subset of Ω including the indices of the non-homogeneous range cells; and \mathbf{p}_i s are non-homogeneous

1. Construct $N_{initial}$ distinct h -dimensional subsets and for each of them carry out the aforementioned iterative procedures, obtaining $N_{initial}$ candidate solutions;
2. Report the subset with the lowest regularized sample covariance determinant chosen among the $N_{initial}$ candidates.

Fig. 1 Algorithm 1: pseudo-code of the ARML method

interference components, representing outliers (modelled at the design stage as deterministic and unknown vectors).

The goal of the outlier censoring procedure is to estimate the outlier index subset Ω_0 and to excise from the data $\mathbf{x}_i, i = 1, \dots, K$, the corresponding samples. Towards this goal, according to the model assumption, the regularised negative log-likelihood function of $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K$ is given by

$$g(\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K) = \ln[\det(\mathbf{R})] + \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i \in \Omega - \Omega_0} \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i \in \Omega_0} [(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{p}_i)^H \mathbf{R}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{p}_i)] + \alpha \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}^{-1}) \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is a regularisation (or penalty) parameter, $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}^{-1}) = \sum_{i=1}^N (1/\lambda_i(\mathbf{R}))$ is the regularisation function, which restricts $(1/\lambda_i(\mathbf{R}))$ from becoming unbounded and thus shrinks the estimate towards a well-conditioned covariance matrix.

Resorting to the GRLF criterion, the RML estimate of Ω_0 can be expressed as

$$\hat{\Omega}_0(\alpha) = \arg \min_{\Omega_0} \left[\min_{\mathbf{R}} \min_{\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_M} g(\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K) \right] \quad (3)$$

where $\arg \min_{\Omega_0}(\cdot)$ denotes the set among the $\binom{K}{M} = ((K!)/(M!(K-M)!))$ M -dimensional subsets of Ω , which minimises the argument.

Minimising (2) over $\mathbf{p}_i, \forall i \in \Omega_0$, yields

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_M} g(\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K) = \ln[\det(\mathbf{R})] + \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i \in \Omega - \Omega_0} \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \alpha \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}^{-1}) \quad (4)$$

Optimising (4) over \mathbf{R} yields

$$\min_{\mathbf{R}} \min_{\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_M} g(\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K) = \ln[\det(\tilde{\mathbf{R}})] + N \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{R}} = (1/K) \sum_{i \in \Omega - \Omega_0} \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{x}_i^H + \alpha \mathbf{I}$.

As a result, the solution to (3) is tantamount to solving the following optimisation problem:

$$\hat{\Omega}_0(\beta) = \arg \min_{\Omega_0} [\det(\hat{\mathbf{R}})] \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{R}} = ((1)/(K-M)) \sum_{i \in \Omega - \Omega_0} \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{x}_i^H + \beta \mathbf{I}$ is the regularised sample covariance matrix (RSCM) with regularisation parameter $\beta = ((K)/(K-M))\alpha > 0$. As to the choice of M , we may exploit some a priori information to obtain an upper-bound.

To solve problem (6), all the possible $\binom{K}{M}$ M -dimensional subsets of Ω are required to be evaluated and the one leading to the lowest regularised sample covariance determinant is finally selected. The computational burden connected with solving the combinatorial optimisation problem could be prohibitive, especially when K is very large. It is thus of interest developing reduced complexity procedures which ensure good quality

solutions. In this respect, inspired by [9], we give the following theorem, which represents the theoretical foundation for the development of an effective regularised outlier censoring scheme.

Theorem 1: Consider a dataset $X = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K\}$, which contains K N -dimensional complex random vectors and denotes by $\Omega = \{1, \dots, K\}$ the indices of the data. Select a $h(h \leq K)$ -dimensional subset of Ω (H_1) and evaluate the corresponding RSCM $\mathbf{S}_1 = (1/h) \sum_{i \in H_1} \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{x}_i^H + \beta \mathbf{I} (\beta > 0)$. Then compute the GIP values based on \mathbf{S}_1 for all the data

$$\mathbf{d}_i(i) = \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{S}_1^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i, \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, K. \quad (7)$$

Now sort \mathbf{d}_i in ascending order and select the indices corresponding to the lowest h values to construct H_2 and compute the RSCM $\mathbf{S}_2 = (1/h) \sum_{i \in H_2} \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{x}_i^H + \beta \mathbf{I}$.

Then

$$\det(\mathbf{S}_2) \leq \det(\mathbf{S}_1) \quad (8)$$

with equality if and only if $\mathbf{S}_2 = \mathbf{S}_1$.

The proof is given in the Appendix.

Like in [9], this procedure is referred to as concentration-step (C-step) since it is possible to acquire a more concentrated RSCM \mathbf{S}_2 (i.e. sharing a smaller determinant than the initial RSCM \mathbf{S}_1). Exploiting this C-step iteratively, a sequence of h -dimensional subsets of Ω associated with a non-increasing regularised sample covariance determinant can be obtained. Furthermore, the iteration procedure must converge due to the finite number of h -dimensional subsets. Consequently, the stopping criterion can be chosen as $\det(\mathbf{S}_m) = \det(\mathbf{S}_{m-1})$ or a maximum number of C-steps N_{cstep} are reached (simulation examples have highlighted that a quite small number of C-steps are sufficient to achieve $\det(\mathbf{S}_m) = \det(\mathbf{S}_{m-1})$ and in all the developed analysis we set $N_{cstep} = 5$).

The above iterative procedure may fall into the local optimum of the minimal regularised sample covariance determinant problem. In order to enhance the probability of falling in the global optimum, a possible way is to take multiple distinct initial subsets and implement the iterative procedures to each subset and select among the output solutions the one leading to the lowest regularised sample covariance determinant. This is the basic idea behind the ARML method. As to the selection of initial subsets, we could choose randomly distinct h -dimensional subsets. The pseudo-code of the ARML method is summarised in Algorithm 1 (Fig. 1).

The ARML procedure can allow for a quite significant reduction in computational complexity as compared with the corresponding RML counterpart. Specifically, when the regularisation parameter is given, the overall computational complexity of the ARML procedure is approximately $O(\max(K, N) N_{initial} N_{cstep} N^2)$ floating point operations (FLOPs)

whereas that of the exact RML procedure is $O\left(\max(K, N) \binom{K}{M} N^2\right)$

FLOPs, with $O(n)$ indicating that an operation requires a number of FLOPs proportional to n .

3 Choice of the regularisation parameter

In order to benefit from the RML/ARML method, it is of paramount importance to properly choose the regularisation parameter β . To this end, the CV technique can be used. It relies on partitioning the original secondary dataset into two subsets, one used as a training set to estimate the unknown parameters and the other used as a validation set to establish the risk associated with the training choice. In the sequel, we exploit the likelihood of the validation data evaluated using the training-based interference covariance estimate as the risk function and adopt the Q -fold CV strategy [11].

Specifically, denote by Φ (of size L) the index set of the candidate validation data (in the subsequent simulations, we set $\Phi = \Omega$), divide Φ into Q (Q is an integer and $1 < Q \leq L$) non-

1. Divide Φ into Q ($1 < Q \leq L$) nonoverlapping groups such that $\Phi = \cup_{q=1}^Q \Phi_q$.
2. For each group, evaluate the risk function (10) for each β_p , $p = 1, \dots, P$.
3. Average all the Q risk functions to obtain the cross-validated risk function (11) for each β_p , $p = 1, \dots, P$.
4. Obtain the estimated regularization parameter $\hat{\beta}$ selecting the specific β_p corresponding to the lowest cross-validated risk function.

Fig. 2 Algorithm 2: pseudo-code of the CV method

overlapping groups such that $\Phi = \cup_{q=1}^Q \Phi_q$, with N_q denoting the number of indices in the q th group (N_q s, $q = 1, \dots, Q$, are often selected to be approximately equal). For the q th group, $\mathbf{X}_q = [\mathbf{x}_i, i \in \Phi_q]$ is used as a validation set whereas all the remaining data $\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_q = [\mathbf{x}_i, i \in \Omega - \Phi_q]$ are exploited as a training set to estimate the interference covariance matrix, whose expression is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_q(\beta) = \frac{1}{K - N_q - M} \sum_{i \in \Omega - \Phi_q - \hat{\Omega}_q(\beta)} \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{x}_i^H + \beta \mathbf{I} (\beta > 0) \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\Omega}_q(\beta)$ is the estimated outlier subset of size M based on the training set $\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_q$ for a specific regularisation parameter β . As a consequence, the risk function for the q th group can be written as

$$f_q(\beta) = N_q \ln \left[\det \left(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_q(\beta) \right) \right] + \text{Tr} \left[\hat{\mathbf{R}}_q^{-1}(\beta) \mathbf{X}_q \mathbf{X}_q^H \right]. \quad (10)$$

The cross-validated risk function is defined as the average over all the Q risks

$$g(\beta) = \frac{1}{Q} \sum_{q=1}^Q f_q(\beta) \quad (11)$$

and the optimal regularisation parameter β is the solution to the following optimisation problem:

$$\hat{\beta} = \arg \min_{\beta > 0} g(\beta) \quad (12)$$

Since we cannot claim either the existence of the minimum nor we can obtain a closed form expression for $\hat{\beta}$, we can define a grid of values $\beta_p > 0$, $p = 1, \dots, P$, evaluate (11) in correspondence of each β_p and select the β_p leading to the lowest value as the optimiser. However, there is no effective method to determine an upper bound or a relatively narrow interval of the optimal β and, hence, to obtain the approximate global minimum of problem (12), it is necessary to search among all the possible values of β in the range $(0, +\infty)$, which is a prohibitive task. Thus, if there is no a priori knowledge about the range of the possible β values, the CV method is hardly to implement. Nevertheless, simulations show that a proper range of β is $(0, 10]$ when the noise power is equal to 0 dB, which is adopted in the sequel. The pseudo-code of the CV method is summarised in Algorithm 2 (Fig. 2).

4 Results on simulated data

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the RML and ARML methods in the presence of simulated data, also in comparison with the GIP [7], RCGIP [8], AML [9], and ML [9] methods. We use the following interference covariance matrix model [14, 15]:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_c + \mathbf{I} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{R}_c denotes the clutter covariance matrix and \mathbf{I} denotes the thermal noise matrix (without loss of generality, we assume that the thermal noise power is one).

In particular, it is assumed an exponentially-shaped clutter covariance matrix, namely

$$\mathbf{R}_c(i, j) = \sigma_c^2 \rho^{|i-j|} e^{j2\pi f_{d_c}(i-j)}, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, N \quad (14)$$

where σ_c^2 denotes the clutter to noise power ratio, ρ and f_{d_c} denote the one-lag correlation coefficient and the normalised Doppler frequency of the clutter, respectively (in the subsequent simulations, $\sigma_c^2 = 20$ dB, $\rho = 0.95$, and $f_{d_c} = 0$).

Besides, assume that N_o outliers are randomly distributed among distinct secondary range cells. The outliers are supposed to have the following model:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = \alpha_i \left[1, e^{j2\pi f_{d_o,i}}, \dots, e^{j2\pi(N-1)f_{d_o,i}} \right]^T, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_o \quad (15)$$

where α_i and $f_{d_o,i}$ denote the complex amplitude and the normalised Doppler frequency of the i th outlier, respectively. Assume that $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{N_o}$ is independent, zero-mean, complex Gaussian random variables sharing the same power, namely, $\sigma_o^2 = |\alpha_i|^2 = \dots = |\alpha_{N_o}|^2$. As to the Doppler frequencies of the outliers, two situations are considered. The former assumes equal Doppler frequency, where $f_{d_o,i} = 0.15$, $i = 1, \dots, N_o$ whereas the latter assumes random Doppler frequency where the normalised Doppler frequencies of the outliers are statistically independent random variables uniformly distributed within the interval $[0.1, 0.2]$. Finally, M_o ($M_o \geq N_o$) denotes the number of data vectors to be removed from the K snapshots (thus $h = K - M_o$).

The performance is assessed using as figure of merit the probability of correctly removing all the outliers, namely, $\Omega_o \subseteq \hat{\Omega}_o$, denoted in the following by P_r . Owing to the lack of a closed-form expression for P_r , the analysis is conducted resorting to standard Monte-Carlo simulations based on 1000 independent trials. Fig. 3 shows P_r versus σ_o^2 for $N = 8$, $N_o = 3$, $M_o = 3$, $Q = 4$, $P = 11$, and $N_{\text{initial}} = 40$ for different values of K and f_{d_o} . Specifically, four cases are considered: (a) $K = 12$ and equal Doppler frequency; (b) $K = 12$ and random Doppler frequency; (c) $K = 20$ and equal Doppler frequency; (d) $K = 20$ and random Doppler frequency. The plots highlight that the performance of all the algorithms improves as σ_o^2 increases. Moreover, the ARML and RML almost share the same behaviour and outperform the other techniques, especially when K is limited. Specifically, for $\sigma_o^2 = 20$ dB, P_r s of the RML and ARML are approximately equal to 1 for all the study cases whereas those of the exact ML are about 0.32, 0.37, 0.89, and 0.96, respectively, for cases (a)–(d). In addition, for the chosen parameters, the behaviour of the RML-type and ML-type algorithms is robust with respect to the Doppler frequencies of the outliers, whereas the GIP and RCGIP normally perform better in the random Doppler frequency case.

5 Results on KASSPER data

This section is devoted to the performance assessment of the ARML algorithm on the challenging KASSPER data. The performance of the RML and ML is not evaluated due to the heavy computational load connected with their computation.

KASSPER is a challenging simulated high-fidelity radar dataset since it considers many realistic heterogeneous effects, such as varying terrain (including mountains and deserts), strong clutter discretises and dense ground targets [13]. The specifications of this database are given in Table 1.

For the sake of simplicity, we only employ the data from the first antenna, namely, $N = 32$. Moreover, we partition the available range cells into N_p segments (i.e. the size of secondary dataset for each segment is $K = 1000/N_p$) and implement the algorithms independently for each segment. Table 2 shows the number of

Fig. 3 P_r versus σ_o^2 of ARML (square-marked curve), RML (circle-marked curve), AML (upper-triangle-marked curve), ML (left-triangle-marked curve), RCGIP (diamond-marked curve), and GIP (plus-marked curve) for $N = 8$, $N_o = 3$, $M_o = 3$, $Q = 4$, $P = 11$, and $N_{initial} = 40$
(a) $K = 12$ and equal Doppler frequency, (b) $K = 12$ and random Doppler frequency, (c) $K = 20$ and equal Doppler frequency, (d) $K = 20$ and random Doppler frequency

Table 1 Specifications of the KASSPER datacube [13]

Parameter	Value
number of range cells	10,000
number of antennas	11
antenna space	0.1092 m
carrier frequency	1240 MHz
peak power	15 kW
pulse repetition frequency	1984 Hz
crab angle	3°
platform height	3000 m
platform moving velocity	100 m/s
platform moving direction	270°
range	30–50 km

correctly censored samples $N_{correct}$ for $N_{initial} = 40$ considering four specific cases: (a) $N_p = 20$ and $M_{o,p} = N_{o,p}$, $p = 1, \dots, N_p$, where $N_{o,p}$ is a known parameter representing the number of the contaminated data in the p th segment; (b) $N_p = 20$ and $M_{o,p} = N_{o,p} + 5$; (c) $N_p = 10$ and $M_{o,p} = N_{o,p}$; (d) $N_p = 10$ and $M_{o,p} = N_{o,p} + 10$. It is quite evident that the results agree with the simulation results in Section 4. Specifically, in the insufficient training scenarios (a) and (b), the ARML ensures a better performance level than GIP, RCGIP, and AML, whereas the four algorithms approximately share the same behaviour when the size of the sample support is sufficiently high ((c) and (d)). However, all the algorithms can only remove a small portion of the contaminated data mainly because of the low outlier power.

6 Conclusion

We have considered censoring data vectors contaminated by outliers from the secondary dataset when the number of training vectors is limited. Specifically, we have derived the RML estimate of the outlier index resorting to the GRLF criterion and have designed an ARML procedure to reduce the computational burden. In addition, we have exploited the CV technique to select the regularisation parameter. The performance of the proposed

Table 2 Number of correctly censored samples

Method	GIP	RCGIP	AML	ARML
case (a)	57	64	57	79
case (b)	79	82	86	95
case (c)	63	63	62	67
case (d)	81	87	90	93

algorithms has been analysed in the presence of both simulated and KASSPER data. The illustrative examples have shown that the ARML represents an effective means to operate in scenarios characterised by a limited number of secondary data. Possible future research might concern the application of the ARML censoring procedure as a pre-processing step to adaptive radar detectors.

7 References

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8 Appendix

Before proving Theorem 1, we give a technical lemma.

Lemma 1: Consider a dataset $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K\}$ including K N -dimensional complex vectors. Then among all the positive definite matrices $\mathbf{\Delta}$, which satisfy $1/K \sum_{i=1}^K \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{\Delta}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \beta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{\Delta}^{-1}) = N$, the RSCM

$$\mathbf{S} = 1/K \sum_{i=1}^K \mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{x}_i^H + \beta \mathbf{I} \quad (16)$$

is the unique matrix which minimises $\det[\mathbf{\Delta}]$.

Proof: Evidently, $1/K \sum_{i=1}^K \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{S}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \beta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S}^{-1}) = N$.

Let $\mathbf{z}_i = \mathbf{S}^{-1/2} \mathbf{x}_i$, $i = 1, \dots, K$ and $\mathbf{\Psi} = \mathbf{S}^{-1/2} \mathbf{\Delta} \mathbf{S}^{-1/2}$. Hence there exists a unitary matrix \mathbf{U} and $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_N > 0$ such that

$$\mathbf{\Psi} = \mathbf{U}^H \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N) \mathbf{U} \quad (17)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \det(\mathbf{\Psi}) &= \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \dots \lambda_N \\ \mathbf{\Psi}^{-1} &= \mathbf{U}^H \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{-1}, \dots, \lambda_N^{-1}) \mathbf{U} \\ N &= \text{Tr}(\mathbf{\Psi}^{-1}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \geq N \left(\prod_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \right)^{1/N} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

From this inequality, the minimal $\det(\mathbf{\Psi})$ is achieved if and only if all the λ_i s are equal to 1, i.e. $\mathbf{\Psi} = \mathbf{I}$. In other words, the minimum $\det(\mathbf{\Delta})$ is obtained when $\mathbf{\Delta} = \mathbf{S}$. \square

Proof of Theorem 1: Using $|H_2| = h$ and the definition of \mathbf{S}_2

$$1/h \sum_{i \in H_2} \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{S}_2^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \beta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S}_2^{-1}) = N \quad (19)$$

Similarly

$$1/h \sum_{i \in H_1} \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{S}_1^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \beta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S}_1^{-1}) = N \quad (20)$$

Moreover, let $\lambda = ((1)/(Nh)) \sum_{i \in H_2} \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{S}_1^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + (1/N) \beta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S}_1^{-1})$, then

$$0 < \lambda \leq \frac{1}{Nh} \sum_{i \in H_1} \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{S}_1^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \frac{1}{N} \beta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S}_1^{-1}) = 1 \quad (21)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} 1/h \sum_{i \in H_2} \mathbf{x}_i^H (\lambda \mathbf{S}_1)^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \beta \text{Tr}((\lambda \mathbf{S}_1)^{-1}) \\ = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left(1/h \sum_{i \in H_2} \mathbf{x}_i^H \mathbf{S}_1^{-1} \mathbf{x}_i + \beta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{S}_1^{-1}) \right) = N \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

According to Lemma 1, $\det(\mathbf{S}_2) \leq \det(\lambda \mathbf{S}_1)$. On the other hand, $\det(\lambda \mathbf{S}_1) \leq \det(\mathbf{S}_1)$, hence

$$\det(\mathbf{S}_2) \leq \det(\lambda \mathbf{S}_1) \leq \det(\mathbf{S}_1). \quad (23)$$

Besides, note that $\det(\mathbf{S}_2) = \det(\mathbf{S}_1)$ if and only if both inequalities are equalities. As to the first, Lemma 1 implies that $\det(\mathbf{S}_2) = \det(\lambda \mathbf{S}_1)$ if and only if $\mathbf{S}_2 = \lambda \mathbf{S}_1$. For the second, $\det(\lambda \mathbf{S}_1) = \det(\mathbf{S}_1)$ if and only if $\lambda = 1$. Combining both yields $\mathbf{S}_2 = \mathbf{S}_1$. \square